

1. X-ray diffraction pattern of rice hull ash.

diffraction (XRD) patterns (Fig. 1). Only the amorphous form of SiO₂ is absorbed by plants. Crystalline SiO₂, from white or pink RHA, is not available for plant uptake.

The RHA was applied to a sandy loam soil on an area basis at 0.0, 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 kg/m². The treatments were replicated six times on two highly susceptible rice cultivars: Early Kolapi 70 and Chimansal 39. A conidial suspension of *P. oryzae* was sprayed on the seedlings at night 15 d after sowing (DAS). The plants' reactions to blast were scored using the *Standard*

evaluation system for rice (0-9 scale) at 30 and 45 DAS.

Applying RHA to the soil in the seedbed had a marked prophylactic effect on rice blast in the seedlings compared with the control where no RHA was applied (Fig. 2). RHA greatly reduced the

2. Effect of rice hull ash applied to soil on leaf blast incidence in rice seedlings.^a 1992-93.

^a scores based on *Standard evaluation system for rice*, 0-9 scale. ^b DAS = d after sowing.

severity of the infection for both cultivars. For Early Kolapi-70, the RHA at 1.0 and 2.0 kg/m² was effective in controlling the disease at 30 DAS, with the seedlings still moderately resistant up to 45 DAS. For Chimansal 39, the seedlings treated with 1.0 and 2.0 kg RHA/m² were resistant to blast up to 45 DAS. The increased resistance to blast could be attributed to the increase in the SiO₂ content of the seedlings (Fig. 2) from the RHA.

The results demonstrate that applying black or gray RHA at 1.0 kg/m² to the seedbed can protect rice seedlings from leaf blast damage without using fungicides, thus helping to protect the environment. (Note: The use of rice hull-fired stoves, such as the FAO-promoted Vietnamese Lò Trâu or the IRRI-designed Ipa-Qalan cookstoves, by farmers for domestic cooking can facilitate collection of RHA.) ■

Integrated pest management—insects

Effect of some fungicides on *Metarrhizium* sp. Sorok: an entomopathogen on insect pests of rice and pulses

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A naturally existing entomophagous fungus, *Metarrhizium* sp. Sorok, was identified in adult brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål), and larvae of armyworm *Spodoptera litura* (F). The insects are important pests of rice and pulses, respectively. Legumes are predominantly cultivated after rice in the dry zone of Sri Lanka. It was observed that the fungicides frequently used to control diseases in a rice - pulse cropping system influenced the development of *Metarrhizium* sp. A bioassay method was used to understand the effects of commonly used fungicides on the development of *Metarrhizium* sp.

Effect of fungicide treatments on *Metarrhizium* sp.^a

Treatment	Concentration (ppm)	Mycelial growth of <i>Metarrhizium</i> sp. (cm) ^b
Control	0	7.2 fgh
Propineb	100	7.7 bcd
	500	7.3 efg
	1000	7.3 efg
Mancozeb	100	7.3 efg
	500	7.4 def
	1000	6.6 ijk
Cuprous oxide	100	7.7 bcd
	500	7.7 bcd
	1000	7.8 abc
Metalaxyl and mancozeb	100	7.7 bcd
	500	7.6 cde
	1000	7.3 efg
Benomyl	100	0.6 n
	500	0.6 n
	1000	0.6 n
Edifenphos	100	6.8 ij
	500	5.4 l
	1000	4.1 m
Sulfur	100	8.0 ab
	500	7.0 ghi
	1000	6.6 ijk
Captan	100	8.1 a
	500	7.8 abc
	1000	7.7 bcd

^a Mean of four replications. ^b In a column, means followed by common letters are not significantly different at 5% by DMRT.

Fungicides propineb, mancozeb, cuprous oxide, a metalaxyl and mancozeb mixture, benomyl, edifenphos, sulfur, and captan were studied. For each, solutions containing 100, 500, and 1,000 ppm were prepared using distilled water. Agar media were prepared using 1 ml of each fungicide solution for every 20 ml of potato dextrose agar and poured into sterile petri dishes. The control sample (0 ppm) was made by adding 1 ml of distilled water. *Metarrhizium* sp. grown in pure cultures were transferred aseptically as agar slugs (6-mm-diameter disks) to the center of each petri dish, replicated four

times in a completely randomized design. Petri dishes were then incubated in the laboratory at 29 ± 2 °C and 76-89% relative humidity. Colony diameters were measured from incubation at 24 h intervals for 5 d. Data were analyzed using Duncan's multiple range test (see table).

Of the eight fungicides tested, benomyl was most toxic to *Metarrhizium* sp., limiting growth to 0.6 cm even at the lowest concentration (100 ppm) (see table). Edifenphos inhibited mycelial growth to a lesser degree, while the remaining six fungicides enhanced

mycelial growth at some or all concentrations.

This experiment clearly indicates the benefits of applying sulfur, captan, cuprous oxide, a metalaxyl and mancozeb mixture, mancozeb, and propineb at low concentrations because they enhanced the development of this entomopathogenic fungus. Application of benomyl should be limited because of its powerful fungicidal action on *Metarrhizium* sp. In an integrated pest management program for a rice - pulse cropping system, fungicides that minimally affect entomopathogenic fungi should be selected. ■

Evaluation of rice, maize, and 56 ricefield weeds as hosts of planthopper *Peregrinus maidis* (Ashmead)

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In the Philippines, rice is reportedly a host of the maize planthopper *Peregrinus maidis*, a vector of several viral diseases in the tropics. We compared the oviposition, egg survival (the number of eggs developing to first instar divided by the total eggs laid multiplied by 100), and nymphal survival (the number of first instar developing to last instar divided by the total first instar multiplied by 100) of

the planthopper on rice, maize, and 56 common ricefield weeds as potential hosts.

The test plants were dug in the vegetative stage from the IRRI farm and transplanted into pots. The plants were allowed to recover for 3 wk. A mating pair of *P. maidis* was introduced onto a potted plant enclosed with a 10-cm-diameter \times 72-cm-high mylar cylinder cage pushed into the soil. The eggs laid were counted by dissecting the plants after 5 d of caging.

More eggs per female (72.7) were laid on maize than on *Rottboellia cochinchinensis* (56.9), *Panicum maximum* (19.6), *Leptochloa chinensis* (15.2), or *Ludwigia octovalvis* (2.2) (Table 1). No

eggs were laid on rice and 52 other plant species in the 16 botanical families tested.

Egg survival was determined by splitting the stems of the plants to recover the eggs and incubating them in petri dishes on moist filter paper saturated with a fungistatic agent (M-tegosept). Egg survival was greatest on *R. cochinchinensis* (96.9%) followed by *P. maximum* (95.4%), maize (94.7%), and *L. chinensis* (89.7%). None of the eggs laid on *L. octovalvis* were viable.

Nymph adaptation showed highest survival (94.1%) on maize followed by 88.6% on *R. cochinchinensis*, 81.7% on *P. maximum*, and 71.9% on *L. chinensis*. Developmental periods for nymphs on

Table 1. Host plant range of *P. maidis*. IRRI, 1990-93.^a

Host	Eggs laid (no./female)	Survival (%)		Nymph development period (d) ^b	Fecundity of surviving females (no. eggs laid) ^c
		Egg	Nymph		
Poaceae					
Maize	72.7 \pm 8.7 a	94.7 \pm 3.5 b	94.1 \pm 3.8 a	17.2 \pm 0.4 a	65.3 \pm 2.8 a
<i>Rottboellia cochinchinensis</i>	56.9 \pm 5.4 b	96.9 \pm 3.2 a	88.6 \pm 8.4 b	127.5 \pm 0.5 b	52.3 \pm 3.3 b
<i>Panicum maximum</i>	19.6 \pm 2.2 c	95.4 \pm 5.2 b	81.7 \pm 8.4 c	17.6 \pm 0.9 b	17.3 \pm 3.8 c
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i>	15.2 \pm 2.5 d	89.7 \pm 8.0 c	71.9 \pm 15.7 d	17.6 \pm 0.7 b	8.7 \pm 1.6 d
Onagraceae					
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i>	2.2 \pm 0.8 e				

^aValues are means \pm standard errors at 95% confidence level. Av of 10 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$) by LSD statistical test. Nonhosts: Aizoaceae — *Trianthema portulacastrum*; Amaranthaceae — *Alternanthera sessilis*, *Amaranthus spinosus*; Asteraceae — *Ageratum conyzoides*, *Eclipta prostrata*, *Synedrella nodiflora*, *Tridax procumbens*, *Vernonia cinerea*; Capparaceae — *Cleome rutidosperma*; Commelinaceae — *Commelina benghalensis*, *C. diffusa*, *Murdannia nudiflora*; Convolvulaceae — *Ipomoea aquatica*, *I. triloba*; Cyperaceae — *Cyperus brevifolius*, *C. difformis*, *C. haplan*, *C. iria*, *C. kyllingia*, *C. rotundus*, *Fimbristylis millacea*; Euphorbiaceae — *Euphorbia hirta*; Fabaceae — *Calopogonium mucunoides*, *Mimosa pudica*, *Sesbania sesban*; Poaceae — *Brachiaria distachya*, *B. mutica*, *Chloris barbata*, *Chrysopogon aciculatus*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*, *Digitaria ciliaris*, *D. setigera*, *Echinochloa colona*, *E. crus-galli* ssp. *hispidula*, *E. glabrescens*, *Eleusine indica*, *Eriochloa procerata*, *Imperata cylindrica*, *Ischaemum rugosum*, *Leersia hexandra*, *Oryza sativa*, *Panicum repens*, *Paspalidium flavidum*, *Paspalum conjugatum*, *P. distichum*, *P. scrobiculatum*; Pontederiaceae — *Monochoria vaginalis*; Portulacaceae — *Portulaca oleracea*; Rubiaceae — *Borreria ocymoides*, *Hedyotis biflora*; Scrophulariaceae — *Lindernia anagallis*; Sphenocleaceae — *Sphenoclea zeylanica*. ^b n = 10. ^c n = 10.